

Data Quality of Crowdsourced Label Transcription: Miniature Lives Magnified

SYNTHESYS3 JRA - Work Package 4 - Objective 3: Crowdsourcing for metadata enrichment of digital images

Task 2 - Development of website to allow crowdsourcing data capture

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Summary

Specimen label data was transcribed from chalcid microscope slides during the Miniature Lives Magnified project using the Notes From Nature platform. To assess the quality of this transcribed data a random subset of transcriptions were selected and manually checked. Of the 312 slides selected, 48% of the slides had an error in at least one of the transcription categories, with some slides having an error in four categories out of a possible six. The two categories with the highest error rate were 'Collector(s)' and 'Host Insect and Plant' (22 and 19%, respectively), followed by 'Collection Date(s)' (16%) and 'Registration Number' (12%), while 'Country' and 'Type Specimen' had the lowest error rates (5% and 2%, respectively). The use of free-text fields for data capture, combined with the complexity of data associated with certain fields, were important factors contributing to the transcription errors. These factors were

confounded further during the reconciliation process of the data as blank fields i.e. no metadata present on the label, were not considered to be data, thus reducing the robustness of using multiple transcriptions per specimen label.

Data Quality Checks

Method

A total of 4,104 microscope slides were transcribed for the initial Miniature Lives Magnified project using the Notes From Nature platform. Each slide was transcribed at least three times and reconciled by Notes from Nature into a single set of transcriptions. A random subset of 312 slide transcriptions were manually checked to assess the quality of the data.

Proportion of Slides with Errors

For the subset of 312 slides, 50% had no error while 48% had at least one error, either incorrect data or missing data, and 2% only had a spelling error (**Figure 1**). For incorrect or missing data, errors were recorded for each of the six categories (Collection Date(s); Country; Collector(s); Host Insect and Host Plant; Type Specimen; Registration Number). The majority of slides only had an error in one category but some slides had up to four category errors.

Figure 1. Proportion of the 312 subset slides with data errors (incorrect and missing data) (**A**). The quantity of errors per category per slide (**B**).

Errors for each Transcription Category

The transcription task aimed to collect information for six categories and the error rates for each of these categories are shown in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2. Proportion of errors for each of the six categories.

The two categories with the highest number of errors were '**Collector(s)**' (22%) and '**Host Insect and Plant**' (19%). As these were both free-text fields, and given the greater complexity of these fields, this is not surprising.

- i) For '**Collector(s)**' [*free-text field*], over half of the errors were from incorrectly recording other information on the slide as the collector (orange bar). These 'incorrect data' errors comprised of recording a place name as the collector or stating the determiner or preparer (names associated with 'Det' or 'Preparer'). The remaining errors were either 'missing data' i.e. collector not captured but stated on slide, either full name or initials following the collection date (yellow bar), or a 'spelling error' of the collector's name (green bar).
- ii) For '**Host Insect and Plant**' [*free-text field*], just under half of the errors were from incorrectly recording the specimen (chalcid) as the host insect, and occasionally the host plant (grey bar). The next most common error was recording incorrect information from the slide as host data (orange bar). Missing data and spelling errors comprised the smallest proportion of errors (yellow and green bars). Between batches of transcriptions an "unclear" option was introduced for free-text fields which may have assisted in reducing the frequency of the specimen's (chalcid) species name error. However, it should be noted that less than a quarter of the slides in the batch with the "unclear" option contained host data, which may have also been a contributing factor.

The next categories were '**Collection Date(s)**' and '**Registration Number**', which both had an error rate of 16 and 12%, respectively.

- iii) For '**Collection Date(s)**' [*drop-down list*], two thirds of the errors were incorrect date information being recorded (orange bar) with the remainder being missing data (yellow bar). Incorrect data comprised of either a range being given instead of a single date, one value i.e. day, from the date not being captured, reversing day and month, or stating the preparation or determination date.
- iv) For '**Registration Number**' [*free-text field*], the majority of the errors were capturing other numbers i.e barcode number, DNA prep number, CIE number (orange bar). For slides where the registration number was not captured (yellow bar), the number was not prefixed with 'BM' or 'Brit Mus' and therefore knowledge of the museum's practices was an advantage.

The two categories with the least errors were '**Country**' (5%) and '**Type Specimen**' (2%).

- v) For '**Country**' [*drop-down list*], all the errors were for missing data i.e. locality information on the slide but the field was left blank. Half of the slides had the country stated in a foreign language (Spanish) or initials given, while for the other half the country had to be determined from the place name i.e. Bournemouth was stated but the country would be the United Kingdom. No incorrect countries were entered.
- vi) For '**Type Specimen**' [*select option field*], all the errors were incorrect data capture in which the slide was a type specimen but this was not captured. These errors generally occurred when there was a conflict between entries i.e. one transcription states 'Yes' and the other 'No' resulting in the field being left blank. There was one exception in which 'Type Specimen' was selected as "Yes" but the specimen did not have a type status designated on the label. In this case two transcriptions incorrectly stated "Yes" for 'Type Specimen', while the third correctly stated "No".

Discussion

Of the 312 slides selected, 48% of the slides had an error in at least one of the transcription categories (Figure 1), with some slides having an error in four categories out of a possible six. The highest number of errors occurred in the free-text fields of 'Collector(s)' and 'Host Insect and Plant' (22 and 19%, respectively), followed by the drop-down list 'Collection Date(s)' and the free-text 'Registration Number' field (16 and 12%, respectively), while the drop-down list 'Country' and select option field 'Type Specimen' had the least errors (5 and 2%, respectively; Figure 2).

The higher error rates in the 'Collector(s)' and 'Host Insect and Plant' fields is likely to be a combination of these fields being free-text and the more complex data associated with these

particular fields, unlike the data associated with 'Registration Number'. Due to the nature of free-text fields there is a no control over the data inputted, therefore as the data complexity increases there will be an increase in the variability in data captured and an increase in the amount of subsequent data cleaning required.

The reconciliation of multiple transcriptions for one specimen into a single record may also have an impact on the variability of the data. For example, the Notes from Nature platform has a fuzzy data matching algorithm to deal with free-text fields that will match a set number of characters and then use the transcription entry with the most characters as the reconciled entry to ensure that the most information is captured. The drawback of this approach is that transcriptions of more complex fields, such as 'Collector(s)' and 'Host Insect and Plant', could have both the correct data as well as additional irrelevant / erroneous data, resulting in surplus information that in fact complicates the data cleaning and increases the time required to complete this process.

In addition, the reconciliation process may introduce data quality artifacts that we need to be aware of to ensure the accuracy of the data captured and effectiveness of the crowdsourced transcription approach. For example, in the current Notes from Nature reconciliation process the most pertinent limitation is that fields left blank i.e. no text entered / selected, do not count as having data entered. For example, if 1 transcription out of the 3 has captured data in a field then this information will automatically be used in the reconciled data (Figure 3).

(A) Original Transcriptions									
Day	Month	Year	Country	Was	Are	Collector1	Collector2	HostInsect	
			Not Shown						
10	7 - July - VII	1909	United Kingdom	No	No	Fred Enock		Anaphes auripes Walker (female)	
			Not Shown	No	No				

(B) Reconciled Data									
Day	Month	Year	Country	Was	Ar	Collector1	Collector2	HostInsect	
10	7 - July - VII	1909	Not Shown	No	No	Fred Enock		Anaphes auripes Walker (female)	

Figure 3. Examples of the original transcription entries (A) and the final reconciled data (B).

As natural history specimen labels vary greatly in the quantity and quality of data that these labels hold, the absence of data is in fact crucial to the accuracy of the record transcribed. As a result, this limitation in the reconciliation process is in fact reducing the robustness of multiple transcriptions per specimen label as you are effectively using only one transcription for that field, as well as reducing the overall accuracy of the data. Many of the incorrect data errors observed

in 'Host Insect and Plant', 'Collector(s)', 'Collection Date(s)' and 'Registration Number' were due to this blank field limitation.

For the drop-down list fields ('Collection Date(s)' and 'Country'), the data captured is more robust for data matching as there cannot be variations in spelling or the amount of data captured. The Notes from Nature reconciliation process uses the majority data matching approach, and if all three transcriptions do not match the field is left blank. The one limitation with the drop-down list fields, particularly evident in 'Collection Date(s)', was that of blank fields not being considered as data. As with the free-text fields, as mentioned above, if the date field is left blank, rather than selecting "Not Shown", any single date entered will automatically be selected for the reconciled data resulting in erroneous data (Figure 3).

In regards to spelling errors, for these particular specimen labels spelling errors only account for a small proportion of the errors (3% for both 'Collector(s)' and 'Host Insect and Plant'; green bars, Figure 2). The low spelling error rate for these particular labels could be due to the large number of typed labels and clear handwriting present and is therefore likely to vary between crowdsourcing projects depending on the types of labels to be transcribed.

Conclusion

Overall findings:

- 'Collector(s)' and 'Host Insect and Plant' had the greatest number of errors (22 and 19%, respectively), most likely as a result of the complexity of the fields, the nature of free-text fields, and the limitations of reconciling free-text data, confounded further by the issue of blank fields not being considered as data (i.e. not metadata present on the label), during the reconciliation process.
- Free-text fields can have a number of inherent limitations as data can be entered in a variety of ways and can easily include irrelevant or erroneous information that may impact on the data cleaning process. Factors such as the complexity of the data vs the data quality of the transcriptions vs the time taken to clean the data vs the importance of the information should all be taken into consideration.
- Inaccuracies in certain types of data will be easier to spot and correct compared to other data types. For example, 'Registration Number' had a 12% error rate, however, the nature of data (i.e. limited complexity and recognisable format etc) would allow for a relative simple data cleaning process. Errors within 'Collection Date(s)' on the other hand, which had a similar error rate (16%), will be harder to detect without checking the slide label. For these particular fields captured during this particular project, addressing the issue of blank entries

and how the data is reconciled would re-establish the robustness of the multiple transcription process and reduce this error rate.

- Certain types of label data may be more complex than others, depending on the background of the transcribers. For example, capturing host data can be complicated due to the latin nature of species names and people's unfamiliarity with the specimen's species name that will also occur on the slide. On the other-hand, for 'Country' the only errors were that of 'missing data' rather than 'incorrect data' i.e. a country or locality was stated on a slide label but the field was left blank. This lack of 'incorrect data' errors could also be due to using a drop-down list rather than free-text data entry thus restricting the data that could be entered. The use of drop-down lists or some other form of restricted data entry, rather than free-text fields, could help reduce the error rate associated with certain types of metadata.

Author Contributions

Louise Allan conducted the data quality checks and analysis. Laurence Livermore and Vince Smith conceived the idea for the crowdsourcing transcription project, which was developed and supported by Margaret Gold. Louise Allan compiled the report and all authors contributed to the revision of the report.

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